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1. Practice abstracts

Best4Soil delivers 50 practice abstracts, a short summary of the projects results, with information that is of practical use for farmers and advisors, the main target group of these practice abstracts. This deliverable reports the second batch of practice abstracts, number 26 - 50.

This second batch of practice abstracts is also reported to the EIP in the specific Excel format. The practice abstracts are edited for publication in pdf on <https://www.best4soil.eu/factsheets>.

Paragraph 1.1 to 1.25 give a copy of the text as written in the EIP practice abstracts, and additional the pictures we included in the edited practice abstracts on the website.

1.1 Practice abstract nr. 26: Representative sampling of compost

It is important to know the quality of the compost that will be applied on the fields. Analysing a representative sample can give this information, steps to take for a sample are following. Material needed: 1 auger (diameter 10 cm, minimum length 100 cm), 1 bucket or plastic bin with strong edges (so that the auger can be hit to drop the compost), 1 plastic sheet of 1.5m x 1.5m, to mix the compost samples (thick plastic (about 0.5mm) but flexible).

Windrow compost: With the auger, make a cross section in up to the center of the windrow every 10-15 meter's. For smaller windrows make at least 5 cuts per windrow. During sieving: take about 1 sample of 2 liters every 15 cubic meter . For smaller batches take a minimum of 3 samples.

Compost storage pile: With the auger, take a deep sample (up to about 80 cm) per 15 cubic meter of compost. For smaller piles take at least 3 samples. Spread the compost over the plastic sheet and mix it well. For biotests, sieve the compost at 10 mm mesh size. Take the required amount of compost: about 1 to 2 liters for chemical analyses, 10 to 12 liters for biotests. Place samples in air-permeable bags. Label the sample bags clearly (date of sampling, charge number, age of compost). Do not use to mark samples with pieces of paper placed in the sample (the paper will decompose quickly). Samples should be analyzed quickly, as values such as mineral nitrogen change rapidly. If the analysis cannot be performed on the same day as the sampling, store the samples in a cool place (4°C). Only a representative sample of compost, taken according to the rules of the art, can give usable results. Database for control of soil borne pathogens.

For a pdf of this practice abstract, including picture(s), please visit www.best4soil.eu/factsheets.

Figure 1: Taking a compost sample

1.2 Practice abstract nr. 27: Compost tea

Producing and applying compost tea is a relatively new practice. It takes advantage of the high diversity of microorganisms and other valuable compounds found within compost. Derived from compost, it contains soluble nutrients as well as useful compounds like metabolites and microorganisms such as bacteria, actinomycetes, filamentous fungi, yeasts and oomycetes. These substances and organisms have a synergistic effect on suppressing diseases and promoting plant growth. Compost tea can be used for the control of soilborne as well as of airborne plant diseases. However, depending on the source material it is also possible that microorganisms pathogenic to plants, animals or humans can occur in the compost tea. Factors other than the source of the compost feedstock that influence the nature of the compost tea are the oxygen content, added nutrients, duration and temperature during the brewing process. For the production of aerated compost teas, which are much more used than non-aerated ones, a specific equipment providing sufficient oxygen during the brewing process is needed. Such brewers are now commercially available and permit the production of aerated compost teas of a high quality. Compost teas can be applied by soil drenching or with a field sprayer. In latter case, the application should ideally take place in the evening or under overcast skies with a pressure, that does not exceed 2 bars.

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Figure 2: Compost brewing

1.3 Practice abstract nr. 28: Growing green manure crops in greenhouses

Green manures are rarely grown in greenhouses. Nevertheless, there are good reasons to do it:

1. Growing deep-rooting plant species (crucifers, Sorghum-Sudangrass) can help to improve the soil structure.
2. Large amounts of easily degradable organic matter are added to the soil by the incorporation of green manures. Consequently, the activity of the soil microorganisms is rapidly increased.
3. Toxic molecules are formed by different plant species. Certain plant species used as green manure crops accumulate significant quantities of such molecules. After the incorporation of these green manures, these toxic substances are released into the soil and eliminate plant pathogens and plant parasitic nematodes.

The “dead” season in greenhouse production in central and northern Europe is the winter season. Plant species which grow well at lower temperatures, such as cereals or crucifers, are best suited for this purpose. Plant species such as Sorghum-Sudangrass, which need high temperatures, should not be used during this period. In contrast, they are very well adapted to the high temperatures, which occur in the greenhouse during the summer season. A reason to grow green manures during the summer season is the much shorter growing duration. The cultivation of green manures in the greenhouse during the winter season (October – February) needs 4-5 months. As the greenhouse is not heated, cold-tolerant species have to be used. Growing during the mid-season (spring, fall) reduces the crop duration by half (2.5 months). The cultivation in summer (June – August) needs 2 months. At this period it is possible to grow thermophilic species such as Sorghum-Sudangrass, which allows to increase drastically the production of green manures.

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Figure 3: Growing cover crops Indian mustard (*Brassica juncea*) in the greenhouse

Figure 4: Incorporating green manure crop sorghum-sudangrass in the soil

1.4 Practice abstract nr. 29: Black root of tomato, *Colletotrichum coccodes*

In recent years there has been an increased occurrence of wilt symptoms on greenhouse tomatoes despite grafting. The reason for this is the pathogen *Colletotrichum coccodes*, a soil-borne fungus. Host plants include solanaceous plants, cucurbits and also several weed species. This pathogen is best known in potatoes in America, where the disease is called "black spot" disease. This term comes from the typical symptoms, the small black dots on the roots, the sclerotia, which the fungus forms for its survival in the soil. Such sclerotia can survive in the soil for over eight years and infest the roots of new host plants. After such an infestation, the fungus destroys the root system, which can then only insufficiently supply the plant with water and nutrients. As a result, the plant shows symptoms of deficiency and wilting. A spread of the fungus within the plant through the sap flow, as is the case with *Verticillium* and *Fusarium* wilt, is not the case with *Colletotrichum coccodes*. The fungus, on the other hand, can spread from the root further upwards into the stem base. From there, it can also infect leaves and fruits. Transmission of the disease via tomato seeds has been demonstrated in Israel. The usual KNVF rootstocks are not resistant to *Colletotrichum coccodes*, so grafting does not protect the tomato from this pathogen. For a pdf of this practice abstract, including picture(s) please visit www.best4soil.eu/factsheets

Figure.5: Damage from *Colletotrichum coccodes* in tomato plants

Figure 6: Sclerotia from *colletotrichum coccodes* on tomtato roots.

1.5 Practice abstract number 30: Verticillium wilt in strawberries

This soil-borne disease, which can also be disseminated latently by young plants, is one of the most important diseases of strawberries. This can lead in the case of a severe infestation and the use of a susceptible variety can lead to the death of the plants before harvesting begins. The disease is caused by the two soil-borne fungi *Verticillium dahliae* and *V. albo-atrum*. These fungi survive in the soil or plant residues in the form of special surviving structures for several years. The fungi penetrate through the roots into the vascular system of the plants and spread throughout the rest of the plant. Over time, the leading vessels become clogged and wilting occurs as a result. The older leaves wilt first and may even die in the advanced stages. As a result of such an infestation, not necessarily fewer, but smaller fruits are formed. This leads not only to a yield decrease but also to a reduction in the proportion of first-class fruit. The wide range of host plants of the *Verticillium* pathogens limits the effect of crop rotation measures. Special attention must be paid to the presence of potatoes, another host plant of *Verticillium*, in the crop rotation. Both *Verticillium* species can be spread via seed potatoes. Further information on the host plant range of the two *Verticillium* species can be found in the Best4Soil pathogen database.

For a pdf of this practice abstract, including picture(s) please visit www.best4soil.eu/factsheets

Figure 7: Verticillium wilt in strawberry

Figure 8: Verticillium wilt, severe damage in open field strawberries

1.6 Practice abstract number 31: Tips soil sampling for nematodes

Good farm management requires a systematic inventory of the nematode situation across your farm. The best strategy for this is to sample crop plots in the fall, preferably prior to a damage-sensitive crop, such as e.g. carrots. This is for two reasons. First, the nematode numbers of non-cyst forming nematodes are highest after harvest and thus can be determined more accurately. Secondly, this sampling period gives sufficient time to take measures, should the results of the nematode analysis give cause to do so. *Pratylenchus* and *Meloidogyne* are found partly in the soil and partly in the root(remains). The extent to which they occur in the roots depends on the pre-crop and the time of sampling. Only an analysis including incubation of the root remains (organic fraction) will give you a complete picture of the numbers of these nematode species. It is not necessary to sample for each damageable crop once the situation has been properly determined and the effect of the intermediate crops is known. The use of fixed sampling strips offers the possibility to monitor the situation per field over the years and to evaluate the management strategy.

The interpretation of nematode results is not always easy. Therefore discuss the results with your advisor and decide which measures are necessary. Also consult the nematode schedule at www.Best4Soil.eu to see what the nematode results mean for your crop plan. Please realise that every sample is a random sample and that the chance of detecting harmful nematodes depends on the method used. To detect infections with potato cyst nematodes or *Meloidogyne chitwoodi* at an early stage, intensive sampling systems are available.

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Figure 9: Sampling for the detection of potato cyst nematodes

1.7 Practice abstract number 32: Intensive sampling for *Meloidogyne chitwoodi*

In a *Meloidogyne* intensive (MELO-I) sampling, an area of 1/3 to a maximum of 1 hectare is sampled before November 15. Compared to a standard sampling, many more stitches are taken and much more soil is processed. As a result, the detection probability is much higher. This is 90% for an infestation that remains after a good host crop. With intensive sampling, a small infestation is detected with great and known certainty.

Intensive sampling cannot be effectively performed during the entire period between crop harvest and new crop in the spring. This is due to the high natural mortality of root-knot nematodes after harvest and during the winter months. During this period the infestation level declines between 50-90%. Until mid-November the detection probability is optimal. After mid-November already half of the root-knot nematodes have died. In spring less than 10 percent is left. An alternative crop/variety can then be grown on an infested area of the field the following year or a control measure can be taken on site in the event of an infestation. It also offers the possibility to cultivate the infested field/strip including a buffer zone to prevent further spread of the nematodes. Moreover, with the results of these samplings and the program NemaDecide, www.nemadecide.com, your consultant can perform scenario studies that predict with high certainty the effect of measures, damage and chances of infestation of these nematodes.

In principle, this method can also detect any other non-cyst-forming nematode better than current methods. But the degree of reliability is not yet known. Moreover, the applicability for this depends on the technique used by the sampler. Ask your sampling agency about it.

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Figure 10: Growers fill tubs with a 60-litre soil sample on which potato or grass is grown in order to assess tuber quality and they take a soil sample for early detection of *Meloidogyne chitwoodi* and *M. fallax*.

1.8 Practice abstract number 33: get nematode information at harvest time

Nematodes can cause major damage to crops, both in yield and quality. In a sensitive crop like carrots, infestations can be detected at an early stage at harvest time, before they become a real large scale problem. The root symptoms give information about the nematode species that are the main problem.

When growth abnormalities are found, it is important to check via a soil and crop sample whether a nematode infection can be confirmed. The information whether an infestation with a plant parasitic species is present is not only important for the carrot crop but for all crops within the rotation.

Infestation by *Pratylenchus penetrans* turns the tap root in a small bulb. An infestation causes blunting of the tap roots, resulting in an irregular quality. An infestation manifests itself patchily in the field.

Meloidogyne chitwoodi or *Meloidogyne fallax* (corn root knot nematodes) causes pimply, but straight carrots. Branching rarely occurs. The lenticels swell to puffy outgrowths. On these symptoms, *M. chitwoodi* and *M. fallax* are indistinguishable. These species cause the same symptoms.

Meloidogyne hapla (northern root knot nematode) leads to branching of the entire root system. On the lateral roots, nodules are visible that form lateral roots on the nodule itself.

Trichodorid nematodes cause a severe infestation in which the seedlings fall off and the roots grow away superficially. Infestations by this nematode usually occur over the entire field. Unlike *M. hapla*, the degree of branching remains limited and no nodules are found on the lateral roots. A poor structure of the soil can give the same picture. In short, it is very worthwhile to stand on the harvester at harvest time and register how the carrots come above the ground.

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Figure 11: At harvest first infestations of nematodes can be found and located. This is the Northern rootknot nematode (*M. hapla*) causing forking of the taproot and showing the characteristic *hapla* root-knots.

1.9 Practice abstract number 34: Free-living nematode *Trichodorus similis* needs attention in Europe

The free-living root nematode *Trichodorus similis* is very common on the sandy soils of Europe. If the numbers get too high, there is a chance of considerable direct damage with financial consequences in the crops; potato, beet, onion, chicory and carrot. When present in high numbers the roots become stubby and stop growing. Some plants suffer more than others, resulting in a very irregular crop. When infestations are very high, seedlings can drop out. Besides this direct damage these nematodes transmit the tobacco rattle virus (TRV) which leads to quality problems in e.g. potatoes and tulips.

You can prevent damage by preceding a crop that is susceptible to damage with a crop that does not propagate the nematode well. For example, grow lilies or spinach.

Unlike *Paratrichodorus teres*, oilseed radish is no more beneficial than other green manures. Also in connection with other nematodes, do not let your green manure stand over the winter. Trichodorid nematodes cause problems especially around the emergence of many crops. The chance of damage is greater in a cold and wet spring. If you suspect that the nematodes are infected with the tobacco rattle virus, choose a potato variety with a high level of resistance/tolerance to TRV. In general, it is valuable to devise an Integrated Nematode Management strategy for each field. By listing the following and implementing them on the farm, problems with plant parasitic nematodes can be avoided:

- Integrated Nematode Management;
- Inventory field history, cropping plan, nematode sampling and damage observed in the field;
- Make a careful choice in crop sequence, choice of varieties, green manures and cultivation frequency;
- Take into account other harmful nematodes on the field;
- Ensure that the soil quality is in order in all aspects;
- Check whether supplementary measures are still necessary;
- Be critical on the origin of plant material;
- Observe good company hygiene.

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Figure 12: Trichodorids cause irregular growth at the beginning of the growing season. Good and bad plants alternate. This is a typical symptom for these free-living nematode species.

1.10 Practice abstract number 35: Integrated Nematode Management (INM)

INM is built on a series of pillars each with their specific management tools. These five pillars are: crop rotation, cultivar choice and crop establishment, soil management, targeted control, and monitoring and evaluation. Each pillar is constructed of numerous control tools that prevent introduction, reduce populations or enhance plant tolerance to nematode damage, completed with some tactical tools to make INM more effective. The best control measure is prevention of introduction and spread of plant parasitic nematodes. Certified seed and planting material is a highly effective tool to prevent invasive nematode species from expanding their range. Rotation, cultivar selection, crop cultivars with resistance or tolerance are available and offer good options to build an effective INM system. Optimal growing conditions help crops to endure nematode damage. Therefore, proper soil management is an important pillar of INM. Nutrient and water management, proper tillage and organic matter are all basic conditions for a healthy crop. In some situations it is necessary to intervene in a targeted way. This could be flooding, solarization, catch crops etc. The targeted use of nematicides is within this pillar.

The monitoring and evaluation pillar is at the same time first and final step in an INM system. Knowing what species are present at what infestation levels make it possible to develop a focussed INM plan and to evaluate whether the results of INM are satisfactory or need restructuring. Historical information about infestations is a good starting point. Sampling provides more detailed information, making possible the development of a tailor made INM. INM integrates knowledge using nematicides as a last resort instead of the first and only solution to think about.

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Figure 13: The book, published in 2021, provides insight into the development of INM strategies around the world. The book is available as an Open Access Ebook free of charge: <https://www-cabi-org.ezproxy.library.wur.nl/bookshop/book/9781789247541/>

1.11 Practice abstract number 36: Factors influencing nematode damage

Besides the numbers in which the different nematode species occur, other factors are at least as important in causing the final damage. For example, a low pH leads to greater damage from Trichodorids in sugar beets and *Meloidogyne naasi* in cereals. Potato is also more affected by *Globodera* when pH becomes low. With higher organic matter content, the risk of yield damage is less. In general, yield damage by nematodes is greater under dry conditions (dry years, drought prone plots). On the other hand, in a wet and cold spring, the probability of Trichodoride damage is higher. Not all crops are equally susceptible to damage by a particular nematode species. There are cultivar differences in tolerance to damage by certain nematode species. In potatoes, cultivar differences exist in tolerance to: *Globodera*, *Pratylenchus penetrans*, Trichodorids (Tobacco Rattle Virus) and *Meloidogyne chitwoodi*. The level of infestation a crop faces in the spring is highly dependent on the preceding crop. For a damage-prone crop, a strongly multiplying pre-crop should be avoided. This information can be found in the nematode schedule of Best4Soil, www.Best4Soil.eu. In some nematode-crop combinations, sowing time has an effect on damage. For root-knot nematodes, damage can be reduced by seeding late. With rising soil temperatures in the spring, root-knot nematodes become active and partially die out as long as no crop is growing. In general, nematode reproduction is lower in crops with short growing periods. Nematode damage can increase with the presence of, for example, fungi and viruses. This also applies to a non-optimal fertilization condition or poor soil structure. When the growing conditions for a crop are suboptimal, the susceptibility to damage becomes stronger.

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1.12 Practice abstract number 37: Self sampling for nematodes, attention points

If you are going to sample for nematodes yourself, take a sample in the proper way, according to the following advice and guidelines:

- Handle the sample carefully.
- Keep the sample cool and dark (4°C) until you send it to the laboratory.
- Refrigerated transport to the laboratory is recommended.
- Specific guides for nematode species:
 - Potato cyst nematode: 1 sample per cultivated variety:
 - minimum of 180 stitches/ha; minimum sampling depth 5 cm sample volume: minimum of 600 ml/ha. 8 kg per hectare is optimal for early detection;
 - sampling aisle: grid: 5 to 11 m wide;
 - Stitches regularly in grids: e.g. 7,5 m x 7,5 m or 11 m x 5 m;
 - diameter: gouge auger 13 mm;
 - always walk in the tillage direction of the crop.
 - Beet cyst nematode: 1 sample/ha:
 - 60 stitches/ha; sampling depth 25 cm;
 - sampling volume: 1200 ml/ha;
 - sampling grid: maximum 11 metres wide;
 - prick regularly in rows of 11 x 15 m;
 - Auger diameter: gouge auger 13 mm;
 - walk in the tillage direction of the crop.
 - Free-living nematodes: 1 sample/ha or on the most suspicious part of the plot (high sandy ridges):
 - For Trichodorids: sample in moist soil;
 - 60 stitches/ha; sampling depth 25 cm;
 - Sample volume: 1200 ml/ha;
 - Sample grid: maximum 11 metres wide;
 - Stitches regularly in grids of 11 x 15 m;
 - Auger diameter: gouge auger 13 mm;
 - walk in the tillage direction of the crop.
 - Root-knot nematode: 1 sample/ha or on the most suspicious part of the plot (high sandy spots):
 - 60 stitches/ha; sampling depth 25 cm;
 - Sample volume: 1200 ml/ha sample aisle: maximum 11 metres wide.
 - Stitches regularly in a grid of 11 x 15 m;
 - Auger diameter: gouge auger 13 mm;
 - walk in the tillage direction of the crop.

When the samples are taken over several hectares, the results become less reliable. So take more samples on larger fields.

When sampling shortly after the cultivation of a crop, the soil sample should be incubated to get the nematodes out of the roots as well. The highest numbers are found shortly after harvest. Therefore sampling before mid November is recommended.

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Figure 14 and 15: Voluntary sampling gives the opportunity to gather detailed information on the distribution of the nematodes within the field

1.13 Practice abstract number 38: Are nematodes the cause of poor crop growth?

When a bad growing spot is discovered in the field, try to take a sample as soon as possible in order to find out if nematodes are causing bad crop growth. Thenematode damage is mostly caused at the beginning of the growing season. Later on, the nematodes that were the cause can be gone. That is why taking samples in the autumn to see which nematode caused the damage in the preceding spring is of little or no use. The steps for taking a plant sample for checking on nematodes are as follows:

- With a spade, dig out a total of 3 plants: at the edge of the bad patch, within the bad growing area and at 5 metres distance from the edge of the bad growing spot in the healthy crop.
- Leave a large clod of soil on the plant that is taken out, so much that it just about fits into a plastic carrier bag.
- You will need 1 - 1.5 litres of soil. Remove the top 5 cm of dry soil. There are few or no nematodes in it.
- Place the plant and the soil carefully in a plastic bag, in such a way that the root ball remains intact.
- Tie the bag tightly to prevent loss of moisture. Adding a tuft of grass or foliage of a crop to the bag helps to prevent dehydration.
- Transport the sample in a cool place (cool box and cooling elements with cardboard between sample and cooling element).
- Provide the sample with a label stating:
 - date and place of sampling;
 - crop, variety, plant or sowing date;
 - probable cause and description of damage, both above and below ground;
 - name and address of the person taking the sample (or grower).
- Take or send the sample to a laboratory and have the soil and roots tested for nematodes.

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1.14 Practice abstract number 39: *Tagetes patula* (Marigold) more than just a cover crop

From Mexico it was known that farmers growing *Tagetes* flowers as chicken feed, had less problems with root lesion nematode (*Pratylenchus penetrans*) in the next potato crop. In the early fifties it was tried to introduce this crop in rose plant production and potato production in the Netherlands. Farmers did not adopt this solution. In the nineties research showed the effectiveness both in apple, roses and potatoes. Nowadays large acreages of *Tagetes patula* are grown in the Netherlands and Belgium with good results. *Tagetes* is sensitive to night frosts and should be sown after the spring frosts. Weeds ask special attention because *Tagetes* has a slow start with poor competition in the first two weeks. Weeds in the *Tagetes* crop spoil the effect of nematode control because many of the weeds are host plants propagating the root lesion nematode. In the temperate zones like the Netherlands, after 3 months the tillage layer is fully rooted and the nematodes are killed for 99%. The decline is that strong that it takes more than 4 susceptible hosts to find higher levels of the nematode again.

Sowing 5-10 kg seed per ha is enough for a good coverage. The seed is not easy to handle. There are little hooks on the seed which causes bridging in the seed bunker. Special adaptations to sowing machines solved the problem. This crop delivers between 625 – 1875 kg effective organic material per hectare. The crop is easily destroyed, especially after the frost, and gives organic matter which is easy to incorporate. Disadvantage is that *Tagetes* multiplies some *Trichodorids* and AG 2-2 of *Rhizoctonia*. Detailed information can be found in the Best4soil databases of nematodes and soil-borne pathogens www.Best4Soil.eu. *Tagetes erecta* is much less effective in controlling nematodes, while *Tagetes minuta* has no nematode-killing effect at all. With *Tagetes patula*, farmers have a colourful solution to the problem of root lesion nematodes.

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Figure 16: *Tagetes patula*, a colourful solution to a nematode problem

1.15 Practice abstract number 40: Soil quality plan (SQP), the foundation for sustainable soil management

Maintaining or improving soil quality requires a knowledge-intensive integral approach. The problem is that the necessary knowledge about the physical, chemical and biological aspects of soil is often fragmented and at present few parties are able to be 'the integrated discussion partner' for the grower. As a result, a grower often receives incomplete or even contradictory advice. The soil quality plan (SQP) is an approach developed by Wageningen University together with advisory parties and growers for working on soil quality in an integrated manner. The wishes and objectives of the grower (crop plan, yields, management measures) are central to this. At plot level, a thorough analysis provides insight into the physical, chemical and biological composition of the soil. These values are then compared with target values and an integrated recommendation for the crop management plan and the management measures is drawn up. In consultation with his advisor, the grower determines which bottleneck or point for improvement for a chosen plot will be tackled first. Two or three scenarios are designed for this. Next, the effect of the developed scenarios on other aspects of the quality of the parcel is examined. This is an iterative process in which the scenarios are weighed for their impact on the physical, chemical and biological aspects of the plot. Based on this, the grower draws his plan. An important component of the SQP is the evaluation. It is determined in advance when and how it will be assessed whether the chosen scenario has achieved the desired result. If not, the approach is adjusted. By screening a farm in this way, a grower obtains a well-founded strategic and operational planning for his business operations. Ad hoc and contradictory advice is thus a thing of the past.

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Figure 17: The discussion between grower and advisors at the kitchen table is a crucial part of the soil quality plan.

1.16 Practice abstract number 41: Suppressive soils are healthy soils

"Suppressive soils are characterized by the absence or low level of a disease in a crop susceptible to the pathogen that causes it, the latter being present in the soil and the conditions being favourable to the development of the disease. That is, they are soils in which there is some factor or factors that prevent the disease from developing, while in similar soils and even in adjacent farms the disease manifests itself.

There are soils with general suppressiveness and soils with specific suppressiveness. The former would resemble the natural soils of forest masses, where there is a very stable biological balance, that is, biostasis.

In agrosystems, we find examples of specific suppressive soils. These are soils that prevent the expression of certain fungal infections or attacks by phytopathogenic nematodes. They are soils in which *Verticillium dahliae* can act, for example, and yet damage by *Fusarium* will never appear, or soils where *Rhizoctonia solani* is never a problem, but the nematodes find fertilized land.

A characteristic that is common to all these soils is the biological character of the suppressiveness. This has been verified experimentally, since suppressive soils cease to be so when they are sterilized. This biological component may involve one or more antagonistic microbial species of the pathogen.

There are examples of suppressive soils to *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *melonis*, *Rhizoctonia solani*, *Heterodera schachtii*. Among the organisms associated with suppressiveness we find fungi of the genera *Fusarium* or *Trichoderma*, and also bacteria such as *Pseudomonas* or *Pasteuria*."

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Fig. 18: Soilborne micro organisms are the origin of suppressiveness for most of the cases.

1.17 Practice abstract number 42: Organic ammendment, biofumigation, biosolarisation and ASD, similar but noticeably different

"An organic amendment is considered to be the incorporation of any type of organic matter into the soil, regardless of the degree of decomposition, generally before sowing or planting. Biofumigation implies an organic amendment, but this organic matter must necessarily be slightly decomposed, and once incorporated, its decomposition within the soil will be activated through wetting. For this it will be necessary to provide one or more irrigations until reaching at least the field capacity of the soil. During the subsequent decomposition process, it will be essential that the soil surface is covered by a film that prevents the evacuation of the volatile compounds generated by said decomposition (a plastic film, or the flooded surface would be good examples of films that are impermeable to these volatile biocides/ biostatic).

Biosolarisation consists of biofumigation in which translucent plastic is used as a soil cover film, and the decomposition time of the incorporated material takes place during the hottest months of the year, thus adding the solarizing effect. It is necessary to reach a good degree of humidity in the soil (between field capacity and saturation) to allow the thermal conductivity provided by the water in the soil.

Anaerobic soil disinfestaion is a soil disinfestation method which implies flooding the soil and the coverage with a tarping impermeable to oxygen. Tarping is not transparent, and the solarisation effect is not expected. A minimum of 16°C is required to activate the anaerobic conditions in the soil."

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Fig. 19: Organic matter ready for application.

Fig. 20: Crops debris used for biofumigation.

1.18 Practice abstract number 43: Grafting vegetables to control soilborne diseases

Vegetable grafting is an ancient technique that has become relevant in recent decades thanks to the success of grafting of conventional varieties on hybrid rootstocks. In many cases, grafting is used as a solution to pathological problems caused by soil fungi. Solanaceae and cucurbits are mainly grafted. The purpose of grafting is to allow the use of plants susceptible to being infected by edaphic pathogens in those soils where the mentioned pathogen is present. Therefore, the rootstock is required to contain resistance or tolerance to the pathogen. The grafting process is carried out by specialized nurseries that have equipment and personnel with sufficient experience. This process requires the sowing of the variety of interest as well as the sowing of the rootstock independently, in order to subsequently proceed with the grafting. Grafting can be done in different ways, being essential to recognize if in the grafted plant, that finally goes to the field, we only have the roots of the rootstock, or that we find the root of the rootstock and that of the variety (permanence of both root systems). From a health point of view, the first situation is preferable, since we eliminate any possible route of infection. It is also important to avoid crossover from the variety (ie, secondary roots of the susceptible variety issuing from stem tissue, which may reach the ground and come into contact with the pathogen in question).

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Fig. 21: Grafted tomato plants in the nursery.

Fig. 22: Crossover of watermelon scion grafted on pumpkin rootstock

1.19 Practice abstract number 44: *Fusarium oxysporum*, a widespread but specific pathogen

Fusarium oxysporum is a species of cosmopolitan fungus that can be found in multiple environments, not only in the soil, but also in dust suspended in the air, in the hair of animals (including humans), in rivers, the sea, and even on the seabed. This high capacity to acclimatize to different environments means that within the species, we can find populations with very different functional characteristics. From an agronomic point of view, most populations of *F. oxysporum* are soilborne fungi that feed on dead organic matter, or that live on the roots of plants, without causing any damage. However, there are small exceptions that are very striking, because they are pathogenic populations that cause significant damage to crops, inducing vascular wilt in most cases, but also causing cankers on roots and crowns. These populations are called special forms (ff. spp.). There are more than 106 well-documented specialized forms. Each f. sp. is pathogenic of a single plant species, with a few exceptions. This fact allows the management of these pathogens through adequate crop rotations. The Best4Soil tool for soil pathogens facilitates the design of rotations taking into account the host range of these fungi (<https://fungi.soilhealthtool.eu/en-gb/Pathogen-scheme>).

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Fig. 23: Morphological diversity of *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *melonis*

Fig. 24: Damages due to *F. oxysporum* ff. sp. *radicis-cucumerinum* specific to cucumber, symptomless on tomato.

1.20 Practice abstract number 45: Genetic resistance to control soilborne diseases

The genetic resistance of plants to pathogens and nematodes is a method that can be perfectly integrated with a disease management strategy that includes other control techniques. It is usual to find commercial varieties with monogenic or oligogenic resistance, which is introduced from a species or variety resistant to the pathogen, into a susceptible variety or type through hybridization programs, normally consisting of crossing through classical hybridization techniques (backcrossing) the species or variety that carries the resistance with a susceptible variety of agronomic interest, for several generations until an offspring that is agronomically valuable and that at the same time carries the resistance to the pathogen. There are many examples of resistance introduced through hybridization programs. In this sense, action can be taken by cultivating varieties with one or more resistance genes, avoiding the repetition of cultivating varieties with the same resistance genes during consecutive campaigns, to prevent the appearance of pathogens overcoming resistance. Another option is to make associations of varieties with different resistant genes in the same plot and in the same cycle. Traditional or local varieties can also show resistance (or tolerance) to certain pathogens, although this is not usual. Regarding tolerance, it is understood as the ability of a plant to withstand certain levels of pathogen infection without expressing symptoms or without presenting damage. Tolerance is a characteristic present in the control of root-knot nematodes of the genus *Meloidogyne*.

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Fig. 25: Screening test for resistance to *Phytophthora* in *Cucurbita* sp. The Upper-right plant shows resistance.

Fig. 26: Variety of tomato tolerant to *Meloidogyne*. Tolerance does not mean absence of infestation but a stronger root system.

1.21 Practice abstract number 46: Soil is a holobiont

Currently there are numerous scientific works, which focus on the study of the biological component of soils as an interconnected system. The concept of soil microbiota (or edaphic microbiome) is widely accepted, and closely related to the perception of the soil as a living ecosystem, or as a holobiont, a being made up of numerous populations of organisms interrelated with each other and without which the normal functionality of that being would not be possible. In this case that being is the soil. As a general rule, most of the microbiota (the microorganisms that inhabit the soil) are located in the first 30 centimeters of soil. We can find different types of microbes, from the tiniest (and microscopic) bacteria to the relatively large mites, springtails, and earthworms. Each type of organism fulfills a function in the soil, its presence in it is not random, but the result of adaptation or acclimatization to this space. Its presence, multiplication and functionality will depend on the processes that take place in the soil. Undoubtedly, the tasks carried out during soil cultivation, before and after it, will influence these microbial communities and vice versa. It is the role of the farmer to favour the appropriate conditions for the proliferation of the biological fraction of the soil that most benefits its health.

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Fig. 27: Microscopic life in soils is quite diverse.

Fig. 28: Red fluorescent cyanobacteria, a pioneer microbe on colonizing soils.

1.22 Practice abstract number 47: Damages on crops due to excessive watering

A typical symptom associated with soilborne fungal and nematode infections is plant wilting. Wilt caused by soilborne pathogens can occur without yellowing the leaves, causing the plant to collapse. It can also be accompanied by chlorosis. Leaf decay (figure 1) is the most obvious sign of wilting, and usually occurs initially during the hottest hours of the day. The observation of these symptoms can lead to think that the plant lacks irrigation while the cause may be quite different. In the case of nematodes and some edaphic pathogens, damage to the roots and crown can be the reason for such wilting. In other cases, when so-called vascular fungi invade the xylem of plants and prohibit the circulation of water through the plant, also wilting occurs. But on other occasions, the cause of this symptom is excess of water in the root zone, without pathogens present in the soil. Waterlogging creates conditions in the environment of the roots that can hinder, if not prevent, the normal functioning of the roots. This limits the absorption of water and nutrients and their distribution by the plant, which leads to wilting. In some crops, flooding or excess water supply induce a thickening of the base of the stem or even cause hypertrophic lenticels, f.e. in peppers. If the waterlogging conditions are prolonged, it can lead to the death of the plant. For this reason, it is very important to control the adequate irrigation provision. The use of tensiometers will allow to know the amount of water available for the plant, without committing excesses.

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Fig. 29: Cucumber plants wilted as a consequence of prolonged excessive watering

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Fig. 30: Hypertrophic lenticells on the crown of a pepper plant

1.23 Practice abstract number 48: Root galling nematodes, general information.

Meloidogyne comprises probably the economically most important plant-parasitic nematode genus worldwide. These nematodes are extremely polyphagous, attacking more than 3.000 plant species and causing damage to vegetables, fruit trees, ornamentals and industrial crops.

Some species as *M. incognita*, *M. javanica* or *M. arenaria* are Worldwide distributed but mainly in Mediterranean, Tropical and Subtropical regions.

Damage thresholds depend on crop, cultivar and environment but densities of 1 juvenile per 100 cm³ of soil can cause significant damage in most crops. Root galling is the most characteristic symptom of these nematodes. In most vegetables, chlorosis or leaf yellowing can be observed in low leaves, developing to plant wilting in most cases. Plants affected by *Meloidogyne* presents above ground symptoms of water and nutrient stress, yellowing, wilting and stunting. Plant death may occur under high infestation levels.

Management of *Meloidogyne* depends primarily on the crop being affected and relies on multiple methods, which can be combined in IPM strategies. Resistant cultivars and grafting on resistant rootstocks is an option for many crops and their use should be a first choice in fields infested by the nematode. Soil biosolarization has proven to be effective in many cases, but it must be applied at least for six weeks and in the summer season, when soil temperatures can reach up to 40-45 °C under a plastic film.

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Fig. 31: Galls of *Meloidogyne javanica* on roots of cucumber

1.24 Practice abstract number 49: Soil fatigue

"Soil fatigue" and "exhausted soils" are concepts present in most countries and agricultural areas. It is a phenomenon associated with frequent growing of the same crop on a field or in a greenhouse. The syndrome presented by plants grown in exhausted soils is mainly manifested by loss of yield, dwarfing of plants, yellowing of plants or delay in development. These symptoms have a partially or completely unknown origin and may be due to various factors or only one. Depending on the cause, soil fatigue can be divided into three types: (1) Physical fatigue due to bad soil structure: shallow soils, cemented by calcium carbonate, gypsum or silica, dry and impenetrable soils, degraded structures, or with deep cracks; (2) Chemical fatigue due to the action of one or more allelopathic compounds, (3) Biological fatigue due to subclinical pathogens. For the three types of fatigue, the addition of organic matter to the soil is a solution that can at least partially replace the effect of a crop rotation. On the physical plane, organic matter will help improve soil structure, porosity, or water absorption capacity. From a chemical point of view, the generation and availability of nutrients will increase with organic matter. And from the biological point of view, the saprophagous microbiota of the soil will be favoured, occupying niches that would be otherwise induced by the so-called subclinical pathogens, which can induce the fatigue effect."

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Fig. 33: Row of pepper plants on an exhausted soil (front of the picture)

Fig. 34: Relationship between soil fatigue and organic matter content

1.25 Practice abstract number 50: Nematodes as bioindicators of soil health

Soil organisms can be used as bio indicators to assess the evolution over time of biological soil conditions across land uses, agricultural practices, contamination processes or climate change. The study of the whole soil biota in an ecosystem is impossible for practical reasons. But there are specific bio indicators for soil health and soil functions (i.e. soil food web, SFW) that can be used as bio indicators.

Soil micro- and meso-fauna is primary composed by nematodes and micro arthropods and have a series of advantages as indicators of the soil ecological functions, compared to other soil organisms: I) Nematodes are, probably, the most abundant metazoan on earth and are present in all terrestrial ecosystems. II) There are nematode species in all trophic groups in the soil. There are bacterivore and fungivore nematodes which regulate microbial populations and affect directly soil nutrient availability, herbivore nematodes that can act as plant parasites and produce large yield losses; omnivore nematodes as indicators of soil food web structure and predatory nematodes that are involved in soil suppressiveness to pests and diseases. III) Nematodes are thus abundant, taxonomically and functionally diverse, and play relevant roles in soil functioning and respond rapidly to chemical and mechanical soil disruption. Nematode-based ecological indices have been widely used in the assessment of soil biological condition."

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Fig. 35: Mouths of nematodes from different trophic groups (from left to right: bacteriovore, nematophagus and phytophagus)